

MICROMECHANICS IN COMPOSITES WITH FIBER/RESIN INTERLAYERS

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ABSTRACT

We report results on the behavior of model composites containing interlayers. To this end, we have coated filaments using chemical or physical vapor deposition routes prior to fabrication of single filament/polycarbonate composite specimens. CVD carbide coatings have been applied onto pitch-based carbon, silicon carbide, and alumina fibers, whereas PVD metallic coatings have been used for PAN-derived carbon fibers. Polycarbonate was selected as a model thermoplastic resin representative of amorphous systems.

Micromechanical behavior has been assessed via tensile deformation of these model composites along their fiber axis. We demonstrate the convenience of this methodology for the determination of: (a) fiber strength as affected by the presence of an interlayer, (b) interlayer strain-to-failure relative to that of the fiber, and (c) effects on load transfer effectiveness imparted by the presence of interlayers.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mismatches in mechanical stiffness between fiber and resin composite systems are known to result in stress concentrations that limit the performance of these materials [1]. In general, these regions where the applied stress is intensified enhance the likelihood of localized cracking that leads to final failure of the component. Thermoplastic resins are offering, in addition to cost advantages, improvements over thermoset matrices in this regard as their toughness level is roughly one order of magnitude higher. However, this improved toughness behavior imposes more demands on the effectiveness of the fiber/resin interface in transferring shear stresses, and its ability to homogeneously distribute loads among fibers. Within this context, fiber/resin interlayers have been postulated in the field as providing a way for improving the interface load transfer effectiveness.

The purpose of the present study is the characterization of the micro-mechanical behavior of interlayers in model composites [2,3]. Special emphasis was given to the role of interlayer strength on the ability of the interphase for sustaining shear loads.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Single filament composite (SFC) specimens were prepared by hot lamination at 200°C of pairs of single filaments between two polycarbonate sheets (each .25mm thick) held at 3900 Pa pressure.

Specimens were cut from the laminates and were 75mm x 9.5mm x .5mm. Table 1 below details average properties for the fibers used in this study.

Table 1. Average Fiber Properties

Name	Main Phase	Manufacturer	Diameter (μm)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (GPa)
Sumica	Al2O3	Sumitomo	15.2	172	1.39
Fiber PP	Al2O3	Du Pont	19.4	260	1.33
Nicalon	SiC	Nippon Carbon	18.1	154	2.74
PBCF (E55)	C	Du Pont	11.0	379	2.10
AU4	C	Hercules	7.1	228	3.42

Rovings of the first four fibers in Table 1 were CVD coated using proprietary procedures to yield SiC/fiber and SiC/C/fiber, with the SiC and C layers having nominal thicknesses of .1μm and .01μm, respectively.

The PAN-derived AU4 fiber was PVD coated in a multi-target sputtering system following standard DC magnetron procedures. Sets of individual filaments were carefully separated from the roving and were mounted on a support that was used for both metallization and SCF fabrication. Single layer coatings sputtered from a stainless steel 304 (S/S) target were deposited to nominal thicknesses of .1μm, .5μm, and 1μm. Bilayer coatings were formed by sequentially sputtering the stainless steel target, followed by the sputtering of an aluminum target. To assure excellent metallurgical bonding between the layers, the aluminum magnetron source was coignited for roughly the last 10% of the ignition time of the S/S magnetron source. Each metal layer was controlled to a nominal thickness of .5μm. Prior to bilayer coating, the AU4 fibers were plasma oxidized to clean their surface.

Each pair of filaments in a given SFC was formed by one coated and one as-received fiber. Tensile specimens were deformed under elongation control conditions using a screw-driven mini-tensilemeter which had a strain resolution better than E-4. Specimen deformation under load control conditions was considered not suitable in view of the strong

loading history dependence of the specimen deflection response. Specimen strain was monitored with an extensometer mounted directly on the specimen, and loads were monitored by an ultra-miniature load cell which was integrated into one of the grips of the mini-tensilemeter. A strain rate of 3.33×10^{-4} /sec was used.

The mini-tensilemeter was small enough to be integrated into the moving stage of an optical microscope equipped with a CCD camera/VCR system, so that deformation/fracture processes could be monitored and recorded for posterior analysis. The moving stage was monitored with a LDVT, so that specific features in the specimen were registered with a resolution of $.5 \mu\text{m}$. We documented in detail the evolution of the filament fragmentation process paying special attention to the unraveling of damage mechanisms. To this end, we stretched the specimens up to selected strain values (well below that required to attain full criticality) and we inspected optically a given region along the filament (typically 15 mm long) to record features of interest such as break locations, debonded areas, etc. We repeated this stretch-inspection cycle at increasing strain levels until no additional filament breaks could be identified, i.e., until the saturation state was fully realized.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fibers studied here had different surface topographies as shown by the SEM micrographs presented in Figure 1 (scale bars denote $1 \mu\text{m}$).

3.1 CVD Carbide Interlayers

Fiber 2 shows a sequence of optical micrographs for a given region in an as-received Sumica alumina fiber at increasing applied strains. Upon fiber failure at 1.8%, clearly distinguishable shear transfer zones (STZ) have formed in the neighboring fragments. As the specimen was stretched, the STZ's lengthened considerably reflecting a poor interphase shear transmissibility. This observation, when coupled with the fact that the surface of the Sumica fiber is very smooth, seems to indicate that shear transmissibility may be governed by the interlocking mechanism in this fiber/resin system. Additional fiber breaks took place at 2.6% and 2.8% applied strain, at which point the fiber attained its saturated state.

Figure 3 shows a Sumica alumina fiber having a SiC interlayer. The SiC did not alter the tensile strength of the fiber. It did, however, improve the interphase shear transmissibility as the following observations suggest: (a) comparison of the STZ's at 2.4% shown in Figures 2 and 3 indicate a shorter STZ for the coated fiber, (b) the STZ lengthening of the coated fiber was much less pronounced than that of the as-received fiber. On the other hand, imperfections in the coating (arrowed feature at 2.6% in Figure 3) induced a STZ lengthening mechanism characterized by abrupt jumps, contrary to the gentle lengthening observed in as-received fibers. The SiC/Sumica bonding was very good as evidenced by the fiber break at 3.7% that took place within a STZ.

The SiC/C bilayer did not alter the Sumica alumina fiber tensile strength. It did, however, dramatically alter the shear transmissibility of the interphase. The top micrograph in Figure 4 shows a coated (top) and an as-received companion filament (bottom) that have broken at around 1.6% applied strain (break in as-received filament has been arrowed). The STZ of the coated fragments is photoelastic inactive when compared to that of the as-received filament. We interpret this behavior as being determined by the presence of the carbon interlayer which, probably, had a very low shear strength. Straining the sample up to 3.5% (bottom micrograph) induced a widening of the gap between the coated fragments, and a lengthening of STZ's of the as-received fragments.

Figure 5 shows 'filament fractograms' depicting the location of filament breaks at increasing strain levels for a given pair of FP alumina filaments (top filament was SiC coated). Similar information is presented in Figure 6, where the top filament was carbon coated. Some fibers fractured in compression during the fabrication of the SFC specimen as a result of shrinkage stresses (crosses indicate the locations of these breaks). However, the residual fragments were long enough that comparative fragmentation analysis could be undertaken. The CVD coatings did not influence the tensile strength of the fibers but they did influence somewhat the interphase shear transmissibility as evidenced by changes in the length distribution of saturated fragments presented in Figure 7 [4]. This influence was much less pronounced than what was observed on the Sumica fibers. This reduced effect may be linked to the fact that these interlayers were much thinner than the average grain size of the FP fiber and, therefore, they had little influence on the interlocking mechanism for shear stress transfer.

The Nicalon SiC fibers were noticeably affected by these CVD coatings. A typical filament fractogram presented in Figure 8 shows both filament tensile strength and interphase shear transmissibility were reduced. The results presented in this Figure are taken from a sample having a carbon interlayer, but they are representative of the other interlayers as well.

The E55 pitch-based carbon fibers were not affected by these CVD coatings.

3.2 PVD Metal Interlayers

Filament fragmentation curves for filaments coated with metal interlayers are presented in Figure 9. These curves depict in a semilog representation the measured average fragment aspect ratio, $\langle L/D \rangle$, as a function of the applied strain ϵ . The coating operations reduced, in most cases, the filament tensile strength as evidenced by the shifts towards smaller strains experienced by the $\langle L/D \rangle$ (ϵ) curves for the coated fibers.

The single interlayers increased the average saturation fragment aspect ratio $\langle L_s/D \rangle$. Figure 10 shows the fragmentation of a given region in a fiber having a $1\mu\text{m}$ S/S interlayer. Arrows in the top and center

micrographs indicate the position of photoelastic-active shear microbands (SMB) that were formed as a result of interlayer failure. The bottom micrograph shows the same region in the saturation state: the copious presence of SMB's has lengthened the STZ's to make the $\langle L_s/D \rangle$ of the coated fiber much longer than that of the as-received fiber. Additional evidence for this SMB-induced STZ lengthening mechanism is given in Figure 11 for a non-saturated fiber have a $1\mu\text{m}$ S/S interlayer. The observed shear stress redistribution took place within a .01% strain interval.

The S/S-Al bilayer had a higher tensile strength wrt the fiber. We do not know if this improvement came about because the fiber was cleaned prior to metallization, or because roughly half the S/S was replaced with aluminum. This replacement could have altered the interlayer defect structure, or could have provided a gradient in modulus thru the interlayer which improved the shear stress transmissibility.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. CVD carbide interlayers reported here had a higher strain-to-failure than their underlying fibers,
2. CVD carbide interlayers did not reduce the tensile strength of the alumina fibers; they did reduce the interphase shear transmissibility in polycarbonate, the degree of which scaled with surface smoothness of the alumina fiber,
3. CVD carbide interlayers reduced both filament tensile strength and interphase shear transmissibility in polycarbonate of the SiC fibers,
4. CVD carbide interlayers had no influence on the E55 pitch-based carbon fiber,
5. PVD metal interlayers reduced the tensile strength of AU4 fibers,
6. Effects of the PVD metal interlayers on interphase shear transmissibility depended on the interlayer strength; low strength interlayers reduced the transmissibility by activating SMB's which relaxed the shear stress within STZ's.

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6. REFERENCES

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FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4

FIGURE 5

FIGURE 6

FRAGMENT LENGTH DISTRIBUTION

FIGURE 7

FIGURE 8

FIGURE 9

FIGURE 10

FIGURE 11

